

Shalimar Rice 1: a new, high-yielding, cold-tolerant, and blast-resistant rice variety for the temperate areas of Jammu and Kashmir

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The states of Jammu and Kashmir lying north of the Indian Union comprise the extreme western part of the Himalayas (32.44° N and 74.54° E). The altitude ranges from 200 to 7,000 masl. The temperate zone, known as “the valley of Kashmir,” is 121 km long and 32 km wide with an altitude of 1,524–2,286 masl. Annual precipitation varies from 700 to 1,500 mm. The temperature remains generally low, varying from –10 °C during winter to 30 °C during summer, with a yearly average of 13 °C. Soil is clay loam with a neutral pH. Rice is grown only once a year because of extreme climatic conditions. In Jammu and Kashmir, rice ranks first in terms of area and production. In 2006, rice was grown on 259,000 ha, with an overall production of 557,400 t and a productivity of 2.3 t ha⁻¹. Generally in demand are varieties with high yield potential and resistance to blast. K39 was the most dominant rice variety from 1980 to 1994; Jhelum was the most popular from 1995 to 2005. These varieties definitely increased rice productivity in Kashmir Valley, but their susceptibility to blast later contributed to a decline in area and productivity. Shalimar Rice 1 was released in 2005 by the State Varietal Release Committee for the valley basin irrigated areas of Jammu and Kashmir. (The variety was named after the world-famous Shalimar Garden built by Mughal Emperor Shah-e-Jahan.)

Shalimar Rice 1 was derived from a cross between IET1444 (Rasi) and China 1007. Rasi has blast resistance and China 1007 has cold tolerance and good adaptability. The variety was developed by hybridization, followed by selection. It was evaluated across target environments from 1993 to 2004 for grain yield, disease resistance, and quality traits (Table 1) with Jhelum as a check variety. Shalimar Rice 1 is medium tall (115 cm), erect, and vigorous, and has a compact plant and panicle type with erect flag leaf and delayed leaf senescence. The basal leaf sheath, apiculus, and stigma are purple in color, which differentiates it easily from other rice cultivars grown in the region. The grain is medium slender with nonglutinous endosperm and nonaromatic features. The 1,000-grain weight

averages 28 g. The variety matures in 132–135 d and has yielded more than 7 t ha⁻¹ in on- and off-station trials (Table 1). The common pests found infesting the variety are grasshoppers, thrips, and beetles, but crop damage does not reach the economic injury level. The variety has shown wide-spectrum resistance to the IC-17 and ID-1 races of blast disease, which are prevalent in approximately 80% of the rice-growing area of Kashmir (Table 2). The physicochemical, cooking, and eating qualities of Shalimar Rice 1 are comparable with those of Jhelum. It has superior grain quality, with 77%, 72%, and 68% brown rice, milled rice, and head rice recovery, respectively. The cooked and uncooked kernels are, respectively, 11.40 and 6.32 mm long and have a length-breadth ratio of 3. Gelatinization temperature is in the intermediate range and so is amylose content (23%). The variety was tested under the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program in 1998 and yielded 57% more than Himdhan and 31.3% more than national check K39. Shalimar Rice 1 performed well under irrigated conditions at fertilizer rates of 120 kg N, 19.8 kg P, 16.6 kg K, and 2.27 kg Zn (convert to elemental format). Following the recommended agronomic practices, the variety yielded 9 t ha⁻¹ in front-line demonstrations at 1,828 masl. The foundation seed sold to farmers in 2005 was 25,000 kg, which increased to 40,000 kg in 2006.

Table 1. Performance of Shalimar Rice 1 (t ha⁻¹) over the years in station and minikit trials in comparison with checks K39 and Jhelum.

Variety	Year												Mean	Yield superiority of Shalimar Rice 1 over check (%)
	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004		
Shalimar Rice 1 ^a	7.9	8.0	10.0	7.6	8.0	7.7	7.7	7.9	7.6	7.9	8.5	8.9	8.0	
K-39 ^a	5.4	5.5	4.9	5.3	5.3	6.3	5.2	–	–	–	–	–	5.4	48
Jhelum ^a	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	6.4	6.7	7.0	7.1	7.5	6.9	15
CD (<i>P</i> = 0.01)	1.15	1.22	2.12	1.35	0.68	0.60	1.82	1.15	0.92	0.68	0.94	0.95	4.20	
Shalimar Rice 1 ^b	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	7.0	7.2	7.1	
Jhelum ^b	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	5.4	5.7	5.5	28

^aStation trials in Kudhwani. ^bMinikit trials in 10 districts, Kashmir Valley, 2002-03.

Table 2. Resistance to blast of some elite rice genotypes, Rice Research and Regional Station, Khudwani, 2001-04.^a

Genotype	Reaction				Mean
	2001	2002	2003	2004	
Jhelum	6.0	5.5	5.5	5.0	5.5
Chenab	5.0	5.2	5.0	5.0	5.0
Barkat	6.0	6.8	6.5	6.6	6.4
Khuch	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0
Madew	8.5	8.5	9.0	8.5	8.6
Shalimar Rice 1	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0

^aIRRI Standard evaluation system, 0–9 scale (0 = immune, 9 = susceptible).